

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

HUMAN-LIKE ROBOTS IN THE "THEATER" OF MARKETING COMMUNICATIONS: SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL REFLECTIONS

Prokopovych L.

*Doctor of Philosophy Sciences, Ph.D. Engineering,
Professor of Department of Cultural Studies and Philosophy of Culture,
Odessa Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0001-8636-9172*

Abstract

Today, the technologies of robotics and artificial intelligence are actively added to the marketing mix, thanks to which the "theatre" of marketing communications acquires a new drama. Therefore, the study of this phenomenon is an actual scientific problem in the interdisciplinary discourse of marketing, cultural studies, social philosophy and philosophy of technology. The purpose of the study is to identify cases of the use of humanoid robots (or their artistic images) in marketing communication and their interpretation in the context of social philosophy and philosophy of technology. The analysis of the collected factual material showed that humanoid robots (or their artistic images) are often used in marketing communication today. There are two main directions of such practice (depending on the goal): use of real robots as promoters or moving mannequins in shop windows; the use of virtual robots created by means of computer graphics and animation in the advertising of certain goods and services. In each of these cases, there are signs of theatricality that make it possible to interpret this phenomenon in theatrical terms and concepts. This approach made it possible to find out that the use of promoter robots is not always effective due to their inability to fully communicate with buyers. However, the use of humanoid robots (real and virtual) as advertising characters is a successful solution, because it allows buyers (clients, users) to feel their involvement in scientific and technical progress, technologies of the future. An analogy with a puppet theater made it possible to understand the reasons for the attractiveness of robots as mannequins in store windows: here there is a feeling of involvement not only with new technologies, but also with art, which can evoke emotions, create the atmosphere of a real theatrical performance on the streets of a big city. In general, the study showed that humanoid robots can be considered as a fundamentally new component of the "theatre" of marketing technologies. This component helps to increase the effectiveness of such communications, so this trend will develop in the near future.

Keywords: humanoid robots, advertising, communication in the "seller-buyer" system, "showcase puppet theater", social demand for new technologies.

Introduction. Scientific and technical progress is conceptualized in philosophy within the framework of the dilemma between social demand for new technologies and possible risks for people and society from the introduction of these technologies [1; 2; 3]. The result of some such reflections is the statement of the emergence of a new socio-technological reality [4; 5]. To a large extent, the formation of this reality is facilitated by marketing communication, especially those types of it in which new technologies are combined with the theatricalization of the sale-purchase process.

Theatricalization, as a means of increasing the effectiveness of communication between a seller and a potential buyer, is characteristic of various spheres of human activity. It is most clearly manifested in exhibition and fair activities, during fashion shows [6] and in other similar events aimed at product promotion.

Currently, robotics and artificial intelligence technologies are actively included in this element of the marketing mix, thanks to which the "theatre" of marketing communications acquires a new drama. Therefore, the study of this phenomenon is an actual scientific problem in the interdisciplinary discourse of marketing, cultural studies, social philosophy, and philosophy of technology.

The purpose of the study is to identify cases of the use of humanoid robots (or their artistic images) in marketing communication and their interpretation in

the context of social philosophy and philosophy of technology.

Methods of research. The main methods of research are methods of analysis and synthesis, which are used to systematize and generalize the discovered factual material.

The theoretical basis for the philosophical interpretation of research results is the concept of theatricality of socio-communicative manifestations of culture [7]. Within the framework of this concept, some types of human activity are studied in comparison with the theater and interpreted in theatrical terms.

Results. Usually, during direct contact between the seller and the buyer (or the target audience), the buyer is the "audience" and the seller is the "artist" (with certain "replies" - recommended phrases, intonations, behavior, etc.). Therefore, the question arises: who (or what) are the robots in this "theatre": are they sellers-artist or just interactive scenery?

This question arises due to the fact that currently two types of robots are involved in advertising: human-like and those that reproduce only some human features and functions (mainly the ability to talk).

For example, in 2015, a female robot appeared in one of Tokyo's supermarkets, who greeted visitors, informed them of what was on sale, and even advised which products to buy. She could speak Japanese, Chinese, Korean and several other languages [8].

But is such communication effective? More precisely, is such communication really communication? After all, the experience of involving the robot Pepper in such a practice brought certain doubts.

The Pepper robot is known for being positioned as the world's first humanoid robot. It was introduced in 2014 as a job with a wide range of capabilities, thanks to which it can perform a variety of duties: from babysitter to shop assistant. The developers claim that this robot is able to study human behavior and adapt to it. Pepper stores all its experience of interaction with users in an artificial intelligence system based on cloud technologies, which is able to quickly teach the robot the necessary actions in certain situations [9]. Thanks to these properties, the Pepper robot quickly gained popularity: its copies began to be used in different countries of the world for various tasks, in particular, for marketing. The media reported that Pepper robots serve customers at the European supermarket chain Carrefour in Spain, the Eobwie.pl shoe store in Gdańsk, Poland.

But in 2018, a modified version of this robot was removed from the flagship store of the Scottish food chain Margiotta after it failed to establish communication between the robot and visitors. This happened not only due to technical shortcomings (the background

noise of the device prevented the correct perception of questions), but also due to, in fact, "intellectual" defects that did not allow the robot to clearly formulate answers to questions about the location of a specific product [10]. That is, real communication, as a process of information *exchange*, does not take place here.

However, it cannot be said that the robot does not contribute to marketing. Outwardly, he is quite attractive, despite the fact that he does not quite look like a person (or, perhaps, on the contrary, precisely because of this): he has no legs, which makes him look like a mermaid on wheels, a monitor is located on his chest. The overall design of the Pepper robot creates a futuristic image that cannot but appeal to a person of the 21st century.

That is, although the robot does not sell in the literal sense of the word, it allows to attract the attention of buyers (clients) and create the necessary atmosphere. In the theater (any) these functions are performed by scenery and props.

This effect of the presence of humanoid robots is actively used by advertising developers to promote goods and services that are not directly related to robotics (mobile communications, cars, household appliances, artificial intelligence services, etc.) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Examples of the use of robot characters in the advertising of various goods and services

The presence of a robot in the frame allows you to create a hint of the involvement of the product (company, brand) in scientific and technical progress, in the technologies of the future. In such advertising, it is not even necessary to use real robots: you can limit yourself to the desired character created by means of computer graphics. With the help of computer animation, you can create a robot with any properties: the ability to speak,

witty jokes, show emotional intelligence and other communication skills that are not yet available to artificial intelligence. Such examples can be seen in the advertising of mobile communication companies, where humanoid robots act as mascots or "faces" of the brand (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Robots as the "face" of brands

But in real life, only experiments with robots that perform the functions of guides, such as the robot guide "Persephone" in Greece [11], are successful, that is, they work in the format of one-way marketing communication (information transfer). For full-fledged communication, it is not enough to know several languages and have a list of products, a plan of their location and instructions in your memory. Something else is needed (intuition, creativity, artistry?) that only humans are capable of. After all, any act of direct contact between a promoter and a buyer is always a mini-performance. Sometimes in such a "performance" the actor is not only the seller, but also the buyer, who is able to impose his own drama in the sale-purchase process.

However, robot developers do not stop trying to create an effective promoter robot. At the same time, some companies no longer seek to reproduce the human likeness in such works, but focus specifically on informational and communicative functions. For example, in 2021, Mars Inc. developed a robot that chases customers and offers them chocolate bars, candies and

chewing gum. The robot was named Smiley. He does not look like a person. It is, rather, a self-moving shelf with sweets. However, this robot is not only created to sell sweets. It also collects data on interaction with customers, using sensors to monitor how customers move through the store and interact with specific products [12].

So, it can be stated that currently robot-promoters are unable to fully communicate with buyers. In the "theatre" of marketing communications, they perform the functions of decorations (sometimes partially interactive), which, however, are able to provide effective advertising, gathering information for targeting, etc.

Another advertising practice that can be compared to theater (with puppet theater) is the display of mannequins in store windows [13]. Today the "window puppet theater" received new dolls – robots.

For example, in the window of a New York store on Fifth Avenue, a robot appeared, almost a living embodiment of the Japanese artist Yayoi Kusama (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. A robot resembling Yayoi Kusama in a store window in New York

The Kusama-robot "draws" multi-colored circles-dots, which have already become part of the famous Louis Vuitton print and have spread across social networks and media [14]. People perceive a robot in a window in different ways: some are frightened, others peer with interest, trying to find similarities and differences with the living original. But the main thing is that the

moving mannequin behind the glass does not leave anyone without emotions. It gives the feeling of a real theater performance right in the middle of a big, noisy city.

Conclusions. The analysis of the collected factual material showed that humanoid robots (or their artistic images) are often used in marketing communication today. There are two main directions of such practice (depending on the goal):

1) use of real robots as promoters or moving mannequins in shop windows;

2) the use of virtual robots created by means of computer graphics and animation in the advertising of certain goods and services.

In each of these cases, there are signs of theatricality that make it possible to interpret this phenomenon in theatrical terms and concepts.

This approach made it possible to find out that the use of promoter robots is not always effective due to their inability to fully communicate with buyers.

However, the use of humanoid robots (real and virtual) as advertising characters is a successful solution, because it allows buyers (clients, users) to feel their involvement in scientific and technical progress, technologies of the future.

An analogy with a puppet theater made it possible to understand the reasons for the attractiveness of robots as mannequins in store windows: here there is a feeling of involvement not only with new technologies, but also with art, which can evoke emotions, create the atmosphere of a real theatrical performance on the streets of a big city.

In general, the study showed that humanoid robots can be considered as a fundamentally new component of the "theatre" of marketing technologies. This component corresponds to society's demand for development, renewal (even if it is only an illusion), so this trend will develop in the near future.

References

1. Kamensky, E.G. & Boev, E.I. (2015). An Innovation Civilization in the Context of the Anthroposphere Crisis of the Technogenic Society. *Asian Social Science*, 11, 4, 328–335. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v11n4p328>
2. Ellul, Jacques (1964). *The Technological Society*. New-York.
3. Habermas, Jürgen (1968). *Technik und Wissenschaft als "Ideologie"*. Frankfurt am Main. ISBN 3-518-10287-7.
4. Trantopoulos, K., Schläpfer, M. & Helbing, D. (2011). Toward Sustainability of Complex Urban Systems through Techno-Social Reality Mining. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 45, 6231–6232.
5. Prokopovych, Lada (2024). Human in New Techno-Social Reality. *Veda a perspektivy*, 1(32): 180-187. DOI: 10.52058/2695-1592-2024-1(32)-180-187.
6. Prokopovych, L.V. (2019). Sotsialno-filosofska «dramaturhiia» pokaziv mod [Socio-philosophical "dramaturgy" of fashion shows]. *Filosofski obrii – Philosophical Horizons*, 41: 199-211. DOI: 10.33989/2075-1443.2019.41.173002. [in Ukrainian].
7. Prokopovych, L.V. (2019). *Teatralnist v sotsiokomunikatyvnykh proiavakh kultury: sotsialno-filosofske doslidzhennia: Monohrafiia [Theatricality in socio-communicative manifestations of culture: a socio-philosophical study: Monograph]*. Odessa: Ecology, 336. ISBN 978-617-7046-78-2 [in Ukrainian].
8. TSN (Apr. 21, 2015). U Tokio vidviduvachiv univermahu obsluhovuie liubiazna zhinka-robot [In Tokyo, visitors to a department store are served by a friendly female robot]. *TSN*. URL: https://tsn.ua/nauka_it/u-tokio-vidviduvachiv-univermagu-obslugovuye-lyub-yazna-zhinka-robot-422528.html
9. Byford, Sam (June 5, 2014). SoftBank announces emotional robots to staff its stores and watch your baby. *The Verge*. URL: <https://www.theverge.com/2014/6/5/5781628/softbank-announces-pepper-robot>
10. Nichols, Greg (Jan. 22, 2018). Robot fired from grocery store for utter incompetence. *ZD.net*. URL: <https://www.zdnet.com/article/robot-fired-from-grocery-store-for-utter-incompetence/>
11. Ponko, N. (Aug. 19, 2021). U Hretsii predstavlyly robota-hida, a bostonski rozrobnyky navchyly svoikh humanoidiv parkuru [In Greece, a robot guide was introduced, and Boston developers taught their humanoids parkour]. *TSN*. URL: <https://tsn.ua/svit/u-greciyi-predstavili-robota-gida>
12. Tran, Tony Ho (March 21, 2021). The maker of M&Ms Built a robot to chase you around the store with candy. *Futurism*. URL: <https://futurism.com/the-byte/maker-mms-built-robot-chase-you-around-store-candy>
13. Prokopovych, L.V. (2024). Dyzain yak tvorche ruinovannia v konteksti teatralnosti buttia [Design as creative destruction in the context of theatrical being]. *Visnyk nauky ta osvity – Bulletin of Science and Education*, 2(20): 1720-1728. DOI: 10.52058/2786-6165-2024-2(20)-1720-1728 [in Ukrainian].
14. Frishberg, Hannah (Jan. 13, 2023). Louis Vuitton installs giant Yayoi Kusama lookalikes, robots at stores. *New York Post*. URL: <https://ny-post.com/2023/01/13/louis-vuitton-installs-yayoi-kusama-lookalikes-at-stores/>